

Electrometric and spectrophotometric determination of *para*-amino salicylic acid^ψ

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Abstract : *para*-Amino salicylic acid (4-amino-2-hydroxy benzoic acid) is useful in the treatment of tuberculosis. A new precipitate based heterogenous electrode has been developed for the electrometric determination of *para*-amino salicylic acid in solution. The characteristics of the electrode was studied.

Keywords : *para*-Aminosalicylic acid, electrometric determination.

Salicylic acid and its various derivatives find a number of applications in medicine for treatment of different diseases. Their outstanding antirheumatic, antifungal actions on human body is very well known¹. The biological action of these compounds vary with substituents present in the ring². The introduction of methyl group increases the oxygen consumption but its rate depends upon the position of methyl group in the ring³. The metal salicylates have also found applications in medicine. *para*-Amino salicylic acid which is useful in the treatment of tuberculosis⁴, chemically is a 4-amino-2-hydroxybenzoic acid. It is marketed as 'MONOPAS' tablets.

Like salicylic acid, *para*-amino salicylic acid (PAS) produces an intense colour when Fe^{III} is added in its aqueous solution. A number of authors have studied the metal-*para*-amino salicylate equilibrium by spectrophotometric method⁵. In past couple of decades a large number of papers have been published on the development and application of electrochemical sensors⁶. These sensors provide real time analysis and are being used for the analysis of several drugs and pharmaceutical formulations⁷. In a review article methods of pharmaceutical analysis with ion selective electrodes for various drug substances including salicylic acid has been given. However no work has been done for analysis of *para*-amino salicylic acid using ion selective electrode. Keeping this in mind, in order to determine the amount of *para*-amino salicylate present in a given solution, a precipitate based electrochemical sensor has been developed. The characteristics of this sensor has been studied and the application of the sensor for the estimation of *para*-amino sali-

cylate in pharmaceutical sample solution has been explored.

The Fe^{III} PAS system was also investigated by spectrophotometry for the determination of amount of PAS present in pharmaceutical sample, so that these determinations could be compared with the values obtained from electrochemical sensor.

Results and discussion

Electrometric technique :

The electrode was conditioned in 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of PAS. In order to measure the electrode response, the electrode potential for a series of solutions in the concentration range 1.0×10^{-1} to 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ was measured with the help of PAS membrane ion-selective electrode and standard calomel electrode as reference electrode. The electrode gave a linear response in the concentration range 1×10^{-1} – 5×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³ of PAS concentration. The slope was found to be 42 mV per decade change in PAS concentration.

To find out the response time, the electrode was first dipped in 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³ solution of PAS and suddenly the concentration of the solutions was changed to 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³. The values of potential changes were noted at every 5 s. A constant potential was obtained after 25 s. A series of solutions containing 1×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ PAS were prepared in which the pH was varied by addition of dilute solution of NaOH or HCl. The potential remains unchanged within the pH range 6–10, (working range). The life time of the electrode is three weeks to 20 months.

^ψPaper was presented in the 40th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Jhansi (2004).

Note

Applications : The electrode was used in the direct determination of *para*-amino salicylate in MONOPAS tablets.

Standard solution of PAS ($1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of the substance [(sodium salt) (B.D.H.)] in distilled water and volume made up to the mark. From this several solutions in the concentration range $1.0 \times 10^{-1} - 1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ were prepared and potential of each solution was measured. From this, calibration curve was constructed by plotting potential against concentration of PAS in semi-log paper.

In order to estimate *para*-amino salicylate in (PAS) tablets, 10 tablets of MONOPAS (Macleods Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) were weighted. These were grounded to fine powder and from this powdered sample (100, 300, 500, 700 and 1000 mg amount) was taken in separate beakers and dissolved in water. After that they were filtered off (No. 42) and filtrates of each sample solution was transferred to separate 100 mL flasks and volume made upto 100 mL with water. From each sample solution 25 mL of solution was taken and the potential was measured using *para*-amino salicylate membrane ion selective electrode.

Using known amount of PAS a series of solutions were prepared and potential of each was measured using *para*-amino salicylate membrane ion selective electrode and from these reading calibration curve was drawn. From the value of electrode potential of different sample solution the corresponding concentration was read from the calibration curve. The results obtained were summarized in Table 1.

From above table it can be seen that there is a fairly good agreement between the amount taken and observed value of MONOPAS tablets. In order to further check the observed value, the spectrophotometric method was also

employed for the determination of PAS in the sample.

Spectrophotometric technique :

Determination of wavelength of maximum absorption :

A solution was prepared by mixing 10 mL of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ PAS, 10 mL of $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ FeCl_3 , 5 mL of $1.0 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sodium perchlorate and then diluting the solution to 50 mL. The spectrum of the solution was recorded in the wave length region 200–600 nm against a blank treated similarly. The wave lengths of maximum absorption are 273 nm and 295 nm and in 490 nm. The colour which forms instantaneously is stable for 40 h.

A series of solutions were prepared with varying amounts of PAS (in the concentration range 8–80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) but fixed concentration of Fe^{III} ion. The pH value of all these solutions were adjusted at 2.35 ± 0.05 by adding dilute perchloric acid to each solution and ionic strength was maintained at 0.1 with sodium perchlorate. After one hour of colour development, absorbance of each solution was measured at 490 nm against blank treated similarly. Then absorbance values were plotted against concentrations of PAS and it was observed that Beer's law was observed in the concentration range 8–80 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of PAS present in the solution. The Sandell's sensitivity was also determined ($0.0976 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$).

The sample solutions were treated in similar fashion and absorbance of each solution was measured. From calibration curve PAS content in MONOPAS tablets was evaluated. From a set of five such measurements the average value of pharmaceutical samples was evaluated which is summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1. Estimation of *para*-amino salicylate in MONOPAS tablets

Sample	PAS present in the sample (mg)	Aliquot taken (mL)	Electrode potential (mV)	Observed value (mg)	
				Average ^a	SD
A	100	25	195	96.28	1.17
B	300	25	217	287.18	11.56
C	500	25	225	481.44	9.44
D	700	25	232	688.38	9.66
E	1000	25	238	984.00	11.56

^aAverage of 5 determinations.

Table 2. Determination of *para*-amino salicylic acid in the pharmaceutical preparation (MONNOPA-Macleods Pharmaceutical Ltd.) using calibration curve

Sample	Aliquot taken (mL)	Absorbance (A)	Amount obtained (mg)	Average (mg)	SD (mg)
T ₁	1.0	0.195	97.13		
T ₂	1.5	0.302	98.54		
T ₃	2.0	0.400	98.18		
T ₄	2.5	0.505	97.55	97.78	0.57
T ₅	3.0	0.604	97.45		

Table 3. Comparison of results obtained by *para*-amino salicylate electrode and by spectrophotometry for pharmaceutical preparation

Amount present (mg)	Amount obtained (mg)			
	Electrode (mg)	SD (mg)	Spectrophotometry	SD (mg)
MONOPAS Macleods Pharm. Pvt. Ltd. 100	96.29	1.17	97.78	0.57

The UV peak 273 nm was also used for spectrophotometric determination of PAS in prepared solution as the intensity of UV peak is higher than the peak observed at 490 nm. Using the absorbance data at 273 nm, from a set of 5 such measurements, the average value of PAS obtained is 98.00 mg and is comparable with the value obtained by electrometric method.

Experimental

Reagents :

Sodium salt of *para*-amino salicylic acid (B.D.H.), FeCl₃ (Ranbaxy Ltd.), perchloric acid (Glaxo Laboratory), sodium perchlorate (C.D.H.) used in this work were of analytical grade. The pharmaceutical preparation of *para*-amino salicylic acid (MONOPAS-Macleods Pharmaceuticals Ltd.) was purchased from retail medical shop and their solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Preparation of Cu^{II}-PAS complex as electroactive material : To a solution of 1.0558 g of *para*-amino salicylic acid, CuCl₂.2H₂O (0.4262 g) solution was added. A dark green coloured precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed and dried at room temperature for 24 h. This precipitate was used as an electroactive material for

preparation of electrode.

Preparation of membrane : Approximately 150 mg of dried electroactive material was mixed with 600 mg of araldite (Ciba-Geigy) and the paste was applied on a Whatman filter paper (No. 42). It was spread uniformly over the filter paper to obtain a 0.1 mm thick layer of the electroactive material within the inert matrix and left in air to dry for 48 h. To prepare the electrode, the filter paper was separated from the membrane by dipping the filter paper containing membrane in a solution of *para*-amino salicylic acid. Any portion of it adhering to the surface of the membrane was removed. A portion of the membrane was cut into a disc and fixed with araldite to one end of a glass tube (diameter 1 cm and length 15 cm) and it was dried for 24 h. The tube was filled with 0.01 mol dm⁻³ *para*-amino salicylic acid solution and kept immersed in solution of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ of *para*-amino salicylic acid for one week. The internal reference electrode was Ag, AgCl and external reference electrodes was calomel electrode. The entire electrode system for the measurement can be represented as

Note

Internal reference electrode (Ag, AgCl)	Internal reference solution 0.01 mol dm ⁻³ <i>para</i> -amino salicylic acid	<i>para</i> -Amino salicylate ion selective membrane	Sample solution	External electrode (S C E)
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Prior to the measurements the entire electrode assembly was clipped in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ solutions of *para*-amino salicylic acid for 24 h

A Philips pH/mV meter (model PR 9405 M) with a silver-silver chloride electrode as reference electrode was used for measurement of electrode potential. Spectrophotometric data were obtained using a digital UV-visible spectrophotometer (SICO Feedback) with 10 mm quartz cuvettes. All measurements were carried out at room temperature (25 ± 2 °C). Doubly distilled water was used in all the experiments.

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